

Sample 02a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0053
	{Fe}	23.8
	{Ca}	16.2
	{Si}	14.2
	{Si, Ca HiP}	9.4
	{Al, Ca}	5.7
	{Ca, Fe}	5.2
	{Si, Ca LoP}	4.0
	{S, Ca}	3.2
	{Al, Si}	2.5
	{Si, S, Ca}	2.0
	{Mg, Fe}	1.6
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.5
	{Mg, Ca}	1.0
	{Si, Fe}	0.9
	{Mg, Si}	0.9
	{Mg}	0.8
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.7
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.6
	{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.5
	{Al, Si, K}	0.4
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.3
	{Al}	0.3
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.3
	{Mg, S, Ca}	0.3
	{Al, S, Ca}	0.2
	{Al, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Na, Si}	0.2
	{S, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Na, S, Ca}	0.2
	{P, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Cl, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, S, Ca}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	16.6
Pellet	1.5
Ore preparation undifferentiated	10.7
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	2.0
BOF converter slag	19.2
BOF converter slag slopping	2.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.3
Desulph slag	0.9
Ca-aluminate slag	4.8
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.8
Olivine flux	0.4
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	2.7
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.2
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.2
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.2
Coal and cokes or soil	6.8
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	7.6
Carbon rich - other	5.3
Cement or BOF converter	1.4
Cement	0.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.1
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.2
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	9.4
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	4.3
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.3
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.7

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	28.9
Site - ore / hot metal	2.0
Site - slag	28.1
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.3
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	2.7
Site - flux / refractory	0.2
Site - refractory	0.2
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.2
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	6.8
Site - carbon-rich other	7.6
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	5.3
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.4
Urban	0.6
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	9.4
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	4.3
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.3
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.7

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 02b

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0021
	{Fe}	25.9
	{Ca}	14.9
	{Si, Ca HiP}	11.5
	{Si}	9.5
	{Al, Ca}	6.2
	{Ca, Fe}	5.7
	{Si, Ca LoP}	3.9
	{S, Ca}	2.6
	{Al, Si}	2.5
	{Si, S, Ca}	2.2
	{Mg, Ca}	1.8
	{Mg, Fe}	1.7
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.6
	{Si, Fe}	1.1
	{Mg, Si}	0.9
	{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.9
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.8
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.7
	{Mg}	0.6
	{Al, Si, K}	0.4
	{Mg, S, Ca}	0.3
	{Al, S, Ca}	0.3
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Al}	0.2
	{S, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Al, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Ca}	0.1
	{Na, Si}	0.1
	{Mn}	0.1
	{Si, P, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, S, Ca}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	14.6
Pellet	1.7
Ore preparation undifferentiated	11.2
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.1
Ore / hot metal	2.8
BOF converter slag	22.0
BOF converter slag slopping	1.4
Slag BOF converter or desulph	2.1
Desulph slag	0.2
Ca-aluminate slag	5.8
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	2.1
Olivine flux	0.6
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	2.9
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.1
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.1
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.2
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.1
Fe-metal rich	0.2
Coal and cokes or soil	4.5
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	8.1
Carbon rich - other	5.7
Cement or BOF converter	0.9
Cement	0.3
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.2
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	4.6
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	6.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.2
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.3
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.5

141 μm

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	27.7
Site - ore / hot metal	2.8
Site - slag	31.7
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	2.7
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	2.9
Site - flux / refractory	0.1
Site - refractory	0.2
Site - scrap	0.1
Urban + site - scrap	0.2
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	4.5
Site - carbon-rich other	8.1
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	5.7
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.9
Urban	0.6
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	4.6
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	6.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.5
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.5

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 02c

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0220
{Fe}	24.1
{Ca}	18.4
{Si}	13.2
{Si, Ca HiP}	10.7
{Ca, Fe}	5.3
{Al, Ca}	4.8
{Si, Ca LoP}	3.7
{Al, Si}	2.9
{S, Ca}	2.4
{Mg, Fe}	1.5
{Si, S, Ca}	1.4
{Al, Si, Ca}	1.2
{Mg, Ca}	1.1
{Si, Fe}	1.0
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.9
{Mg}	0.7
{Mg, Si}	0.7
{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.6
{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.5
{Na, Al, Si}	0.4
{Al, Si, K}	0.4
{Al}	0.3
{Na, Si}	0.3
{Al, S, Ca}	0.2
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.2
{S, Ca, Fe}	0.2
{Mg, S, Ca}	0.1
{Mg, Al, Si, K}	0.1
{Cl}	0.1
{Al, Ca, Fe}	0.1
{S, Fe}	0.1
{Zn-LA1}	0.1
{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.1
{Na, Cl, Ca}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

141 μm

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	13.5
Pellet	2.1
Ore preparation undifferentiated	13.3
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	2.4
BOF converter slag	20.9
BOF converter slag slopping	1.8
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.3
Desulph slag	0.5
Ca-aluminate slag	3.7
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.2
Olivine flux	0.3
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	3.5
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.2
Fe-metal rich	0.1
Coal and cokes or soil	8.2
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	6.6
Carbon rich - other	3.4
Cement or BOF converter	1.5
Cement	0.1
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.1
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	9.1
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	4.8
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.2
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.1
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.1
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.9

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	28.8
Site - ore / hot metal	2.4
Site - slag	28.1
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.5
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	3.5
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.2
Urban + site - scrap	0.1
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	8.2
Site - carbon-rich other	6.6
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	3.4
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.5
Urban	0.2
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	9.1
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	4.8
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.3
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.9

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels